

Modified 'Vancouver Scar Scale' / Pectoralis muscle major flap harvest

Gender:	o male	o female		
1	Pigmentation Scar 1	0 normal	1 light	
		2 moderate	3 high	
	Vascularization Scar 1	1 normal	2 pink	
		3 red	4 purple	
	2	Pigmentation Scar 2	0 normal	1 light
			2 moderate	3 high
		Vascularization Scar 2	1 normal	2 pink
			3 red	4 purple
3		Pigmentation Scar 3	0 normal	1 light
			2 moderate	3 high
		Vascularization Scar 3	1 normal	2 pink
			3 red	4 purple
	4 Which incision line is best in regards of the visibility?			
	Scar 1	Scar 2	Scar 3	
	5 Which incision line is most likely stigmatizing?			
	Scar 1	Scar 2	Scar 3	

6 Which incision line makes you feel uncomfortable when you are showing your naked upper body to your partner or children?

Scar 1

Scar 2

Scar 3

7 With which incision line you would go to swimming?

Scar 1

Scar 2

Scar 3

8 With which incision line you would feel watched?

Scar 1

Scar 2

Scar 3

9 Which incision line would lead to questions of the cause with your relatives/friends/colleagues?

Scar 1

Scar 2

Scar 3

10 Which incision makes you feel uncomfortable?

Scar 1

Scar 2

Scar 3

11 Which incision do you prefer mostly?

Scar 1

Scar 2

Scar 3

12 If you are the surgeon and you can choose between the skin incisions: which incision line you would perform?

Scar 1

Scar 2

Scar 3

13 Which incision line you would strictly refuse?

Scar 1

Scar 2

Scar 3

14 Which incision would make you refusing the whole surgery?

Scar 1

Scar 2

Scar 3